

Observations on the natural history of *Anadia ocellata* Gray, 1845 (Squamata: Gymnophthalmidae)

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INTRODUCTION

Lizards of the family Gymnophthalmidae are exclusively found in the Neotropics and reach their highest diversity in the Amazon basin of South America. A few species in this family range into Central America and some even occur on Caribbean islands (SAVAGE, 2002). Previously these so-called “microteiids” were lumped with the “macroteiids” into the family Teiidae, which includes whip-tailed lizards, racerunners, and tegus. Currently, the large, fast-moving macroteiids are considered separate from the diverse group of small to medium-sized microteiids and each is assigned to a different family, Teiidae and Gymnophthalmidae respectively (PRESCH, 1980, 1983).

Members of the family Gymnophthalmidae are mostly small and secretive fossorial or subfossorial species of slender build. However, the morphological and ecological variation found within this group is such that it is near impossible to generalise characteristics or morphological traits unique to this family. Even the small subset of gymnophthalmid lizards that ranges into Central America (a mere 14 species) displays a variety of forms that includes skink-like leaf litter inhabitants (*Gymnophthalmus*), nearly limbless fossorial species (*Bachia*), semi-aquatic crepuscular stream dwellers (*Neusticurus*) and arboreal bromeliad inhabitants restricted to the rain forest canopy (*Anadia*). Each of these species displays morphological features and adaptations specific to the

Rara Avis rainforest.

Photo: T. Leenders

micro-habitat it inhabits. The immense variety within this family, combined with the often small number of museum specimens available for study, is largely the reason why the taxonomic status of this large group of lizards is still in flux. The systematic placement of the taxa within the Gymnophthalmidae at the genus and even sub-family level is continuously changing (e.g. CASTOE et al., 2004; DOAN, 2003; DOAN & CASTOE, 2005; PELLEGRINO et al., 2001). As is presently understood, the family Gymnophthalmidae comprises approximately 37 genera and more than 180 species.

Anadia ocellata

Approximate distribution range of *Anadia ocellata*. This species may be more widespread but is rarely observed.

Art work: T. Leenders

GEOGRAPHIC AND ECOLOGICAL DISTRIBUTION

Anadia ocellata is the northernmost member of its genus and one of the northernmost representatives of the family Gymnophthalmidae. The only gymnophthalmid found farther north, *Gymnophthalmus speciosus*, inhabits the arid and semi-arid parts of Central America, ranging as far north as southern Mexico and the Yucatan Peninsula (KÖHLER, 2003). The distribution range of *Anadia ocellata* comprises mountainous regions in Costa Rica and western Panama. Within this geographic range, this rarely observed species inhabits foothill and middle elevation forests (520-1,200 m asl) in areas with a relatively high annual rainfall (SAVAGE, 2002). The consequent high humidity provides ideal conditions for epiphytic vegetation and *Anadia ocellata* is predominantly found inhabiting the epiphytic masses of vegetation seen on the branches of even the highest rainforest trees. This specific microhabitat preference most certainly accounts for the perceived rarity of this species, as it tends to live in places far removed from human observers. However, long-term observations in Rara Avis rainforest preserve (Heredia Province, Costa Rica, GPS N10°16.916' W84°02.740'; 710 m asl) indicate that this species is in fact quite common in appropriate habitat.

NATURAL HISTORY

Anadia ocellata is a small, long-tailed lizard with a strongly attenuate head and a body and tail covered in smooth, quadrangular scales that are arranged throughout in continuous whorls. Adults may reach a total length of up to 216 mm, with a snout-vent length between 50-75 mm. The tail is extremely long, and is generally considerably more than twice the snout-vent length (SAVAGE, 2002). However, many individuals of this species sport a secondarily regenerated tail because of autotomy. The limbs are short and on several occasions individuals have been observed moving with only the long tail as a means of propulsion. Generally, the limbs are held closely adpressed against the body. This type of locomotion has been seen when the lizard is examining narrow crevices (e.g. inside small bromeliads, or when squeezing into insect burrows in dry branches) and no 'leg room' is available, but also when the animal is placed on the ground or on a flat surface and tries to escape in a serpentine fashion. Individuals have been observed walking in a slow, deliberate, very salamander-like hand-over-hand fashion on epiphyte covered branches in the rainforest canopy, as high as 40 m above the forest floor. More frequently though, the animals can be seen weaving in and out of the mossy, humus-

Strangler fig rainforest epiphyte.

Photo: T. Leenders

Anadia ocellata uses its long tail as an anchor when moving through the precarious confines of its treetop habitat.

Photo: T. Leenders

rich matrix that covers the branches and forms the substrate for the hemi-epiphytes, plants that use aerial roots and true roots to tap into the nutrients accumulated in the canopy (e.g. many *Ficus* sp. and aroid species, such as *Philodendron* and *Monstera* sp.).

Invariably, the lizard probes small crevices and pockets in the moss mats with its head, using its tail as an anchor to allow the animal to make sudden lunges at escaping insect prey without running the risk of losing its footing in this precarious habitat. On one occasion, an individual was observed crawling through the leaf axils of a bromeliad when suddenly the animal sprang from the interior of the plant in pursuit of a flying insect it startled and was left dangling over a 30 m drop suspended only from its tail (LEENDERS, 2001). Undoubtedly, these

animals will occasionally plummet from the canopy but their small size and low weight will most likely allow them to survive such a fall unharmed.

It has been suggested that the distribution range of *Anadia ocellata* coincides with that of the large 'tank' bromeliads (genus *Guzmania*) as these large epiphytic plants known for their associated fauna could pose a suitable habitat (HEYER, 1967). These extremely agile and slender lizards appear most at home in the tight axils of surprisingly small *Tillandsia* species (LEENDERS, 2001) and in the thick moss mats that cover tree branches and trunks. Individual *Anadia ocellata* have also been found inside rotten tree stumps and in dry, insect-perforated branches.

Apart from the observations in the rainforest canopy, dozens of individuals have been

found closer to and even on the ground. Invariably, these observations were made in a clearing (approximately five acres) surrounded by primary and secondary rainforest. *Anadia ocellata* is frequently encountered climbing on the rafters of a tin-roofed building located near the edge of an old-growth secondary forest, as well as in the thatched roof of another building located in the centre of this clearing. An orchid garden, bordered by a primary forest edge, seems to attract a fair number of these lizards as well, and they are not infrequently found on the individual orchids or inside the associated mossy substrate. On one occasion, an adult *Anadia ocellata* was seen on the ground in the middle of the grassy clearing moving away from the forest edge towards a building. Possibly the relatively warm, dry and sunny climate that prevails in the forest clearing matches the prevailing climate in emerging tree tops, whereas the forest interior could be too cold, dark and humid for these lizards to survive. This could potentially explain why out of more than fifty observations, none were made in the understory of the rainforest.

COLOUR PATTERN VARIATION

The colour pattern of *Anadia ocellata* is quite variable and has led to some taxonomic confusion. The most distinctive pattern element is a row of three to eight distinct light spots along the flank, starting above the insertion of the front limb. Generally at least a few of these spots are outlined in black pigment, forming eyespots or 'ocelli' (hence the specific epithet '*ocellata*'). These light spots are located on a dark bronze to brown lateral field that extends from the side of the head, along the body

Male *Anadia ocellata* displaying its almost uniform copper coloured dorsum. Note how the light dorsolateral lines are almost indistinguishable.

Photo: T. Leenders

Bromeliad covered tree.

Photo: T. Leenders

and onto the tail and is bordered above by a light, irregular line that often forms a zigzag pattern on the tail. The mid-dorsal area, between the dorsolateral light lines, is quite variable and may be uniform, spotted or blotched, with a metallic green, bronze, or brown colour. The ventral surfaces are white to cream, occasionally with some light mottling (SAVAGE, 2002).

Variation in this colour pattern, and the absence of a sufficient number of preserved specimens for comparative studies (only three specimens and the description of an old desiccated type were used for this study) led Edward Taylor (TAYLOR, 1955, 1956) to believe that there were as many as three distinct geographic races of this species present in Costa Rica. Based on their colour pattern and limited scalation characteristics he described *Anadia metallica metallica* from the Central Pacific slope, *Anadia metallica attenuata* from the Caribbean slope and *Anadia metallica arborea* from northwestern Costa Rica (TAYLOR,

1955). He indicates in his descriptions that the amount of separation between these forms is likely not sufficient to warrant specific status for any of them, but that additional specimens are needed to resolve the situation (*Anadia ocellata* is represented by less than twenty specimens in museums world-wide).

OFTEDAL (1974) analysed the intraspecific variation within *Anadia ocellata* in his systematic study on the genus and compared fifteen specimens – probably close to all preserved specimens of this species available in museum collections world-wide. He synonymized *Chalcidolepis metallica* Cope, 1875 with *Anadia ocellata* Gray, 1845, thereby giving *Anadia ocellata* seniority

more diverse than that described by TAYLOR (1955) can occur in a single location (see accompanying figures – all taken in Rara Avis), thus confirming Oftedal's conclusion. In addition, recent observations have shed a somewhat different light on the colour and pattern variation within this species. On 7 March 2005, during an on-site tropical biology course, two individual *Anadia ocellata* were collected from the rafters of a classroom building in Rara Avis around noon. A third individual was caught at 9:30 AM the next day in the above-mentioned orchid garden. Two of the lizards showed distinctive dorsolateral light lines enclosing a darker mid-dorsal field; one individual even displayed a secondary light field forming within the dark mid-dorsal field

Female *Anadia ocellata* with an unusual colour pattern. The dark mid-dorsal field displays a lighter centre that extends posteriorly from the top of the lizard's head; for the rest the mid-dorsal field is uniformly dark.

Photo: T. Leenders

over *Anadia metallica*, and also concluded that the three subspecies described by Taylor were merely examples of extreme colour and pattern variation within a single species. In addition, the variation in scale row count and number of femoral pores did not stand up to further examination and did not correlate with any geographic distribution patterns. OFTEDAL (1974) therefore restricted the Costa Rican members of the genus *Anadia* to a single monotypic species, *Anadia ocellata*.

A CASE OF SEXUAL DIMORPHISM?

Observations on *Anadia ocellata* in Rara Avis over a period of twelve years have shown that a range of colour patterns even

(see figure). The remaining individual displayed an almost uniform coppery coloration with only very faintly outlined dorsolateral lines, but with distinctly demarcated ocelli. Both colour patterns were observed frequently in Rara Avis, although the uniform colour pattern appears to be less common.

The two individuals collected only minutes apart in the rafters of the class room building – one with a clearly outlined pattern, and the uniformly coloured individual – were placed together in a plastic observation cage containing some branches and dry leaves for the intended purpose of taking photographs and morphometric measurements. Almost immediately the uniformly coloured individual started chasing the darker coloured individual and initiated

Anadia ocellata mating. Note the striking difference in coloration between the male (uniform copper colour) and the female (presence of distinct light dorsolateral lines).

Photo: C. Dolan

courtship behaviour, followed shortly after by a neck bite and mating (see figure). Courtship was brief (2-3 minutes) and consisted of head nudging by the male, and rubbing the male's chin on the back of the female. The actual copulation lasted approximately 30 seconds.

No clearly demarcated sexually dimorphic field characteristics are known for *Anadia ocellata*. TAYLOR (1955) used the number of femoral and precloacal pores present on his specimens as an indication of geographic race. This notion was quickly discarded by OFTEDAL (1974) who determined that the

variation in the number of pores represents sexual dimorphism (8-11 in males, 2-6 in females), and the latter characteristic has since been used to determine the gender of museum specimens. So far, too few individuals have been examined to be able to make strong correlations between colour pattern and gender. However, upon close examination of the colour descriptions and black and white photographs in TAYLOR (1955), his observations appear to agree with the possibility that female *Anadia ocellata* are more vividly marked and more brightly coloured than males, who appear to

Anadia ocellata

Note the presence of a transparent window in the lower eyelid of *Anadia ocellata*.

Art work: T. Leenders

10 mm

have a more faded coloration and less pronounced dorsolateral light markings. In extreme cases, male *Anadia ocellata* may appear uniform bronze to copper on their upper surfaces. As a result of this more muted coloration the lateral series of ocelli becomes much more pronounced in males, as the black outline of the white spots contrasts sharply with the lighter lateral coloration. In individual *Anadia ocellata* with the dark mid-dorsal field and clearly defined dorsolateral light lines, the ocelli on the side of the body are often much less visible, while the bold light lines and zigzag pattern on the tail are much more prominent.

Colour patterns showing a series of light spots on the sides of the body variably outlined in black are commonly seen in many South American Gymnophthalmidae and even in some Gekkonidae (e.g. see colour plates in DUELLMAN, 2005; BARTLETT & BARTLETT, 2003; AVILA-PIRES, 1995) and are therefore presumed to be an evolutionarily advantageous characteristic. A possible function for this generalised pattern has not been determined yet. One possibility is that the intensity of the ocelli is a sexually dimorphic signal, more pronounced in males and made even more visible through a uniform or faded colour pattern when compared to the more boldly coloured females. A similar dichromatic pattern can be seen in photographs of both male and female *Cercosaura ocellata bassleri* (a South American gymnophthalmid) in BARTLETT & BARTLETT (2003, plates 158A & 158B), in which the overall colour pattern of both sexes is comparable, save for the much more strongly defined ocelli in the male lizard. Possibly this particular pattern element could have a signal function to convey sexual fitness or territorial dominance. Hopefully, future observations and studies may further clarify this issue.

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SUMMARY

Field observations on *Anadia ocellata* in Rara Avis (Costa Rica) are presented to indicate habitat use in this lizard, which was previously considered rare. Further, a chance observation on a courtship and copulation session suggests sexual dimorphism in colour patterning.

SAMENVATTING

Jarenlange veldwaarnemingen aan *Anadia ocellata* in Rara Avis (Costa Rica) bevestigen mijn indruk dat deze hagedis niet zo zeldzaam is als altijd werd gedacht. Het is eerder het verblijf in haar voorkeurshabitat, epifytische vegetatie in de boomkruinen van het regenwoud tot op wel veertig meter hoogte, dat ervoor zorgt dat de soort sporadisch wordt gezien. Er bestaat bovendien weinig museummateriaal en de variatie in kleur en tekening ervan kon slecht geduid worden. Ook het externe geslachtsondscheid bleek lastig. Een toevalswaarneming van een paring bevestigde het ontstane vermoeden dat de duidelijker en contrastrijker gekleurde dieren vrouwtjes betreffen, terwijl de mannetjes fletser gekleurd zijn, soms zelfs egaal brons- of koperkleurig. Hierdoor vallen de laterale ocellen bij hen meer op.

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Female *Anadia ocellata*. The mid-dorsal field is heavily marked with dark blotches.

Photo: T. Leenders

